

Porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome viruses (PRRSV) affect every major pig-producing country in the world

PRRSV cause **reproductive failure** in sows and **pneumonia** in piglets

Resulting in **major economic losses** e.g., \$664 million in the USA and €1.5 billion in the EU each year

PRRSV has a **high mutation rate**, which has resulted in a huge diversity of strains

Pigs normally mount immune responses, which are unable to protect against different PRRSV strains

However, repeated exposure of sows to PRRSV results in **broadly neutralising antibodies**.

The REPRODIVAC solution:

We will isolate antibodies capable of broadly neutralising PRRSV and use these to identify the highly conserved structures they recognise on the virus surface (the PRRSV 'Achilles' heel'). We will then engineer vaccines to display these structures so that pigs mount immune responses that would protect them against any PRRSV strain.

